

Addressing the Frame Problem using a Probabilistic-BDI Cognitive Architecture

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Abstract- This article briefly presents a probabilistic-BDI cognitive architecture, dubbed CernoCAMAL, that has extended the CAMAL (Computational Architectures for Motivation, Affect, and Learning) architecture by incorporating a probabilistic reasoning capability in its BDI model, and also integrating all the valenced predicates across its architecture. The design and implementation of cognitive architectures is a useful tool for understanding cognition in a situated agent. A major problem that arises with situated agents that are able to deliberate is the Frame Problem. CernoCAMAL's Probabilistic Reasoner addresses the Frame Problem by limiting the scope of the propositions its deliberative component must re-consider and re-evaluate in the light of its actions by using a Memory Trail.

Keywords- *Cognitive Architecture; BDI; Probabilistic Reasoning; Affect; Motivation; Memory; Anchoring Problem; Frame Problem*

I. INTRODUCTION

The CAMAL [1] model is an example of a general class of integrative cognitive architectures; drawing together a number of threads in Cognitive Science and Artificial Intelligence, such as perception, action, decision making, motivation, affect, and learning. CAMAL was developed from ideas incorporated in Guardian [2], ACT-R [3], CRIBB [4], CogAff [5], and the cognitive architectures of Singh and Minsky [6]. CAMAL is, essentially, a UTC (Unified Theory of Cognition) [7] that tries to answer many of the questions that comprise Norman's Cognitive Science agenda [8]. CAMAL uses a variant of the a-CRIBB reasoning model [9, 10] i.e. a BDI (Belief-Desire-Intention) model and an affect model, plus a motivational blackboard. CAMAL has never included any probabilistic reasoning capability, although multi-dimensional metrics are used to rank motivations and goals, and also manage affect [11].

The primary aim of the CernoCAMAL research project [12] was to investigate how CAMAL could be extended to reason probabilistically about tasks and domain model objects through perception, and how Probabilistic formalism could be integrated into its BDI model to coalesce a number of mechanisms. The impetus for this investigation was considerable evidence that probabilistic thinking and reasoning is linked to cognitive development and plays a role in cognitive functions, such as decision making and learning [13, 14, 15]. This leads us to believe that a probabilistic reasoning capability is a vital part of any system that attempts to emulate human intelligence computationally. In other words, probabilistic reasoning is an essential aspect of the process of cognition and, therefore, must be considered in any adequate description of it.

II. COGNITIVE ROBOTICS

Cognitive Robotics (both simulated and embodied) is a growing research field that draws on a number of disciplines. Whether in simulated or physical testbeds, cognitive robots and agents provide an essential tool when investigating the interaction of cognitive architectures and the environment. Cognitive robots and agents have been used to investigate

many different aspects of Artificial Intelligence, such as mapping and localization techniques [16, 17], robot perception [18], and robot learning [19, 20, 21]. This research builds on a previous use of a mobile robot to investigate a specific area of Cognitive Science known as the anchoring problem [22]. The anchoring problem describes the problem of generating and maintaining links between symbols and perceptual data.

Hybrid architectures seek to avoid the disadvantages of their component architectures, whilst retaining all their benefits. A common hybrid architecture is the reactive-deliberative architecture [23]. Here, we present an architecture consisting of several different elements, including an extended BDI model, a probabilistic reasoner, a reactive component built from many different reactive behaviours; a belief-desire-intention (BDI) schema; a distributed model of affect; an association construct; a domain model; and a motivational blackboard that links all these sub-systems together. This architecture addresses another specific area of Cognitive Science known as the frame problem. The frame problem describes the problem of how to keep an agent's model of its environment consistent and up to date [24, 25].

III. CERNO-CAMAL

The belief-desire-intention (BDI) model [26] is a schema that determines the actions of an agent based on its beliefs and desires. A belief is a statement about the confidence of a proposition. The confidence the agent can have in a belief can vary. In the BDI model, beliefs are based on input from the agent's perceptual system, and its previously-held beliefs. The agent's desires are a set of goals which the agent wishes to achieve. The agent's current desires are based on its internal state, possibly its emotional state, and its previously-held desires. Coupling the agent's beliefs and desires generates a set of intentions, or plans of action, to achieve its goals. For example, the agent has a goal to hit a ball. Its perceptual system generates the belief that there is a ball to the right. The agent can implement a set of plans to turn the agent right and move forward.

The CRIBB (Children's Reasoning about Intentions, Beliefs' and Behaviour) model was developed to investigate reasoning in young children [27]. This schema was implemented as a computer model to simulate knowledge and the inference processes of a child solving problems [4]. The CRIBB model was further developed to include affective affordances [9, 10]. For Cerno-CAMAL, a major difference to the standard BDI model is that different degrees of belief are ascribed to belief statements, according to the source of the belief. This was accomplished by extending the CAMAL belief structures to incorporate degrees of belief.

CernoCAMAL makes use of a hybrid reactive-deliberative architecture based on the control system approach to mind [28]. A control state is a behavior internal to an agent. Control states

can exhibit external behaviors (such as obstacle avoidance) or reflect and control internal states (such as beliefs). In essence, control states can be a number of things, such as beliefs, desires, motivators, etc. They can be considered as general behaviors within an agent, and therefore can be modified or updated at any time by some other processes.

Scientific evidence highlights the fundamental role of affect in rational and intelligent behaviour [29]. Since there appears to be a requirement for something analogous to affect in artificial cognitive systems, it has been conjectured to use affective control states which makes affect the basis of a consistent control language across a cognitive architecture [9, 11, 28, 30, 31]. Further research proposes that motivation, too, plays a fundamental role in a variety of cognitive functions [32]. From the viewpoint of mind as a control system, motivation can, thus, be thought of as a control state. Furthermore, motivators (that are dispositions and tendencies to assess situations and respond to those situations and assessments in a certain way) can provide a context and impetus for reasoning about events, and also a basis for goal-directed behaviors. They are, therefore, often used as a generic framework that draw all these control states (beliefs, goals, etc.) together. It now seems reasonable to conclude that motivation and affect can be co-joined in perception and cognition. Given the fact that motivations are essentially more encompassing than goals since they include not only the descriptions of goals but also an affective context for those goals, plus the fact that motivators are often used as a generic framework since they can draw all the control states of a cognitive architecture together, the use of control states to develop cognitive architectures leads to the use of affective and motivational control states. The following sections briefly introduce some of the main components of the CernoCAMAL architecture.

A. Probabilistic -BDI Model

One of the limitations of the BDI model is the lack of any explicit mechanism to express degrees of belief. CAMAL represents beliefs as categorical states; prioritized only by a CAMAL preference model, using belief preference operators. Given that our current work on this theme presents an affect-and affordance-based core for mind, it seems reasonable to conjecture that beliefs, too, should be grounded in the use of affect with the aim to be consistent across different domains, tasks, and levels of processing. This will be compatible with the way in which the affect and motivational models operate throughout CAMAL; having an associated affective magnitude that can fluctuate according to success or failure associated with that element. Effectively, affect will serve as a decision metric and affective values as a currency across the entire architecture. We have, therefore, represented CernoCAMAL belief statements as graded states, using a probabilistic formalism. The Extended Belief Structure (EBS) represents the degrees of belief numerically, using clauses of the form:

belief (Descriptor, Source, Time, DegreeOfBelief).

The EBS associates a probability value *DegreeOfBelief* with every belief statement in CernoCAMAL which defines the degree to which the belief statement is believed to be true. This will enable the computation of degrees of belief, and using the BDI and affect models to determine the agent's intentions, actions, and behaviors. It will also allow the entire BDI model to run using numeric affective values to prioritize choices made over a current belief set.

CernoCAMAL's Probabilistic-BDI model provides a method to control the flow of information through the deliberative component. It determines the intentions, actions, and behaviors of the cognitive agent based on its beliefs and desires.

B. Affect & Motivational Models

Affect is defined in terms of information processes and representational structures across a cognitive architecture. It is qualitatively defined as negative, neutral, or positive, and can be mapped numerically over the interval $[-1.0, +1.0]$. The use of affect and affective control states makes affect the basis of a consistent control language across a cognitive architecture. It also allows external events and objects to take valenced affordances, and internal mechanisms to be prioritized via valenced processes. Adding affect results in more effective processing and task management [9, 11]. The affect model distributes affect values across the entire cognitive architecture, rather than have a centralized emotion module. This is made possible by the use of associations. An association is a construct that contains a BDI combination, as well as an associated affect value (*insistence*). Associations take the following form:

association(Belief, Desire, Intention, Insistence).

This association value is one of the main factors in deciding (at the deliberative level) the next action of the cognitive agent. The architecture maintains various beliefs about the environment it is operating in, and several possible goals that relate to that environment. It also has a number of different plans of actions or intentions or behaviors that may correspond to specific reactive sub-architectures that can be activated. Associations effectively provide a method for a cognitive agent to keep track of all these possible belief-goal-action combinations, as well as containing a key value that indicates their relevance and significance to the agent at a given time – their association value. These combinations detail the correct action required to achieve a specific goal given a specific belief.

Similar to the affect model, the motivational model contains an affective value in the structure of its motivational blackboard. The motivational blackboard acts as a global workspace - a global structure that holds all the relevant information about an agent's environment, attributes, properties, beliefs, desires, current state, previous states, etc. This metaphorical blackboard, analogous to Baars' Global Workspace [33] is potentially accessible by all the processes of an agent. The knowledge and information held on the motivational blackboard can be divided into several distinct areas: beliefs that the agent can have about its environment, beliefs that the agent can have about its own internal state, desires that the agent can have about the objects in its environment, intentions that the agent can have to achieve its goals, associations that are used to manage the BDI and affect models, and a motivator that contains the result of the operation of knowledge sources. The focus is often on the motivator as a representational form that enables perception, affect, cognition, and behavior to come together and interact. In effect, a motivator is a representational schema that is used as a generic framework to bring together aspects of perceptual and cognitive processing, such as perception, affect, and behavior. Motivators not only manage and manipulate the affective and motivational control states present at the 'deliberative' level, but may also trigger appropriate intentions, actions, and behaviors at the 'reactive' level, such as selecting a suitable

reactive sub-architecture. Motivators can, thus, be thought of as the result of the operation and execution of the various knowledge sources of a motivational blackboard. Motivators take the following form:

motivator(Goal, Association, Deterministic, Cycles, Intensity)

The Intensity element is an affect value that gives the importance of the motivator to the agent. The schema also contains the agent's chosen goal, plus the appropriate association selected to achieve that goal, which obviously contains the intention of the agent as well. The Cycles element gives the number of cycles the reactive component should run for. The Deterministic element is set to either false or true. If set to true, the reactive component would override any reactive/behavioral failure in achieving a goal or other conditions until the end of the cycles, or until the goal is met. If set to false, the reactive component would return the first possible action that the deliberative-reactive interface selects, based on the appropriate goal-association combination. Once a goal and a relevant association are chosen, the motivator-update knowledge source of the motivational blackboard uses them to update the motivator

C. Domain Model

In addition to Probabilistic-BDI, affect, and motivational models, CernoCAMAL makes use of domain models. Even though its cognitive architecture contains only two layers of reactive and deliberative, it is vital that relevant information about its attributes and properties along with its surrounding environment be incorporated into its cognitive architecture. This incorporation is achieved by the use of its (propositional) domain model. Using a domain model is a method of instantiating the relevant information about a cognitive agent's attributes and its surrounding environment into its cognitive architecture. The domain model, once loaded, is distributed across the cognitive architecture, at both the reactive and deliberative levels. It provides information on the agent's attributes and its surrounding environment; it defines the types of objects to be found within the agent's environment (physical or simulation); it defines some of the possible beliefs that are most relevant to the agent; it defines the relationships between the stated beliefs; it defines the goals that the agent can have; it provides a list of all the possible actions the agent can undertake; it provides the objects' perceptual profiles (i.e. the information required to recognize an object), etc.

Statements about the agent's environment at the deliberative level pertain to the possible beliefs the agent can hold. These constitute the beliefs used in the BDI model. These statements are present on the motivational blackboard at the deliberative level, unlike the environment domain model which had components present at both the reactive and deliberative levels. These statements are on the motivational blackboard, and provide information on the goals that the agent can have and the actions that the agent can take. These constitute the desires and intentions used in the BDI model. Goals take the following form:

Goal(Descriptor, SuccessCondition, Importance).

The Descriptor is a description of the agent's goal. The SuccessCondition is the belief descriptor required for the goal to be achieved. The Importance is an affect value detailing the goal's affordance; meaning how important the goal is to the agent.

D. Probabilistic Reasoner

The development and implementation of the EBS in CernoCAMAL allows for the inclusion of degrees of belief for different information sources. The following is the initial domain model assumptions made over the apriori of various sources of belief:

degree_of_belief(perception, 0.9).
degree_of_belief(deduction, 0.7).
degree_of_belief(assumption, 0.5).

It is also noteworthy that a belief descriptor could be the apriori probability of an object being present in the environment:

apriori_prob(Object, DegreOfBelief).

which is clearly in the form of assumed knowledge. CernoCAMAL's probabilistic reasoner (CPR) given the list of domain model objects and assumed degree_of_belief for various sources of belief, can compute the posterior probabilities, assign them to the appropriate belief descriptors, and reason probabilistically about the number of objects and their instances that may be present in the environment. As an example, consider a possible initial configuration of having one sphere, one prey, one predator, and no unidentified objects in Tile World simulation environment. This application area uses a graphical world created using SWI-Prolog Version 5.8.0 – an abstract tile world with operators that affect the world, incorporating a CernoCAMAL agent, several edible spheres, preys, and predators. The initial configuration can be represented by the following statements:

belief(apriori_prob(object, 0.0), assumption, 1, 0.5).
belief(apriori_prob(sphere, 0.3), assumption, 1, 0.5).
belief(apriori_prob(pred, 0.3), assumption, 1, 0.5).
belief(apriori_prob(prey, 0.3), assumption, 1, 0.5).

This initial configuration assumes that if there is one object, then it is equally likely to be a sphere, a prey, or a predator, hence the probability of every domain object being present is 1/3 or 0.3 with a 0.5 degree of belief since the statements are assumptive. Known exemplars of the above object classes are identified via instances, e.g. prey2. The feedback messages received from the reactive layer take the following form:

[reactive_cycles(N) / Messages].

The deliberative layer uses the reactive feedback messages to construct updated beliefs. It, then, updates the time and activates the deliberative component with the updated beliefs. The power of CernoCAMAL's CPR lies in its probabilistic interpretations of the predicates pertaining to various instances contained in reactive feedback lists. Note that the instances that were destroyed; i.e. eaten and could not be re-generated when stumbled upon and the instances that were lost, but could be re-generated when stumbled upon. This intelligent probabilistic reasoning capability that keeps track of the instances is made possible by CernoCAMAL's memory facility.

E. Operational Overview

CernoCAMAL uses a Probabilistic-BDI schema to drive a motivational blackboard. The inclusion of degree-of-belief in the structure of its belief predicates enables the architecture to select a focused belief set that reflects its current activities, as highlighted by actions, objects, and agents referenced in a current motivator. The motivator enables goal revision and the selection of the next goal based on goal importance and current beliefs and goal success. The deliberative processing of these

constructs allows the selection of an appropriate action related to specific objects and tasks. This, in turn, drives motivator revision using the association construct, which in turn enables belief-desire-intention combinations to be ranked based on the likelihood of their success (association values). The goal importance, association insistence, motivator intensity, and degree-of-belief are all underpinned by affordances; i.e. they are all consistently grounded in affect. Together, they allow motivators to persist or be updated by new goals, associations, etc.

At the reactive level, perceptual data from the test beds' sensors are passed to the deliberative layer. This perceptual message is posted to the motivational blackboard and reasoned about by the CPR. Then, the belief-update module uses the new information to modify its belief set. The goal-update then uses the updated belief set to determine if the current goal has been achieved, and what the new goal is. The association-update then uses the new belief and goal set to determine the relevant action or intention. Whether in simulated or robotic test beds, sensory information is mapped onto belief structures. Belief affordances (degrees of belief) define the degree to which the belief statement is believed to be true. The affective insistence measure allows the control of external behavior through the building of associations that link beliefs, goals, and intentions.

IV. CPR & FRAME PROBLEM

The following are a comprehensive set of possible elements constituting the reactive feedback list, accompanied by their interpretations and actions to be taken by the CPR. These predicates are applicable to both simulation worlds, but mostly specific to the predator-prey terrain, e.g. ate(preay). Understanding these mechanisms is a prerequisite to making sense of the experiments.

LOST

1. Lost an object in its general form, e.g. lost(sphere) → all instances of that object are lost + all know_of and instance_of are retracted + memory of all the lost instances is formed + a suitable message is displayed.
2. Lost an instance of an object that has never been found before, i.e. illegal argument for the predicate lost → a suitable message is displayed.
3. Lost an instance of an object that has actually been found before → that particular instance is lost + know_of and instance_of for that particular instance are retracted + memory of the lost instance is formed + a suitable message is displayed.

ATE

1. Ate an object in its general form, e.g. ate(sphere) → only one instance of that object is eaten (the most-recently found instance, i.e. Recency Conflict Resolution) + that particular instance is destroyed + know_of and instance_of for that particular instance are retracted + a suitable message is displayed.
2. Ate an instance of an object that has never been found before → i.e. illegal argument for the predicate ate → a suitable message is displayed.
3. Ate an instance of an object that has actually been found before → that particular instance is destroyed + know_of

and instance_of for that particular instance are retracted + a suitable message is displayed.

FOUND

1. Found an instance that has already been found before → a suitable message is displayed.
 2. Found an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form, that there is a memory trail of a previously lost instance of it → that previously generated lost instance is re-created, instead of a new incremental one + a suitable message is displayed + know_of and instance_of for that particular instance are asserted.
 3. Found an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form, while the instance list of that object is empty, i.e. that object is definitely the first to be found → a new unique instance is generated + a suitable message is displayed + know_of and instance_of for the new unique instance are asserted.
 4. Found an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form for the second time (i.e. two founds in a single reactive feedback list) → the first found refers to a previously found instance + the second found generates a new unique instance + a suitable message is displayed + know_of and instance_of for the new unique instance are asserted.
 5. Found an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form, while it can refer to a previously found instance, rather than generating a new unique instance (rather than extending the instance list) → found refers to that previously found instance + a suitable message is displayed.
 6. Found an illegal instance (an instance that cannot possibly be recognized as that instance!) → a suitable message is displayed.
- ##### NEAR
1. Near an instance that has already been found before → a suitable message is displayed.
 2. Near an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form, that there is a memory trail of a previously lost instance of it → that previously generated lost instance is re-created, instead of a new incremental one + a suitable message is displayed + know_of and instance_of for that particular instance are asserted.
 3. Near an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form, while the instance list of that object is empty, i.e. that object is definitely the first to be near to (to be found) → a new unique instance is generated + a suitable message is displayed + know_of and instance_of for the new unique instance are asserted.
 4. Near an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form for the second time (two nears in a single reactive feedback list) → the first near refers to a previously found instance + the second near generates a new unique instance + a suitable message is displayed.

displayed + know_of and instance_of for the new unique instance are asserted.

5. Near an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form, while it can refer to a previously found instance, rather than generating a new unique instance (rather than extending the instance list) → near refers to that previously near (found) instance + a suitable message is displayed.

6. Near an illegal instance (an instance that cannot possibly be recognized as that instance) → a suitable message is displayed.

HIT

1. Hit an instance that has already been found before → a suitable message is displayed.

2. Hit an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form, that there is a memory trail of a previously lost instance of it → that previously generated lost instance is re-created, instead of a new incremental one + a suitable message is displayed + know_of and instance_of for that particular instance are asserted.

3. Hit an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form, while the instance list of that object is empty, i.e. that object is definitely the first to be hit (to be found) → a new unique instance is generated + a suitable message is displayed + know_of and instance_of for the new unique instance are asserted

4. Hit an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form for the second time (two hits in a single reactive feedback list) → the first hit refers to a previously found instance + the second hit generates a new unique instance + a suitable message is displayed + know_of and instance_of for the new unique instance are asserted

5. Hit an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form, while it can refer to a previously found instance, rather than generating a new unique instance (rather than extending the instance list) → hit refers to that previously hit (found) instance + a suitable message is displayed

6. Hit an illegal instance (an instance that cannot possibly be recognized as that instance) → a suitable message is displayed

Attacked

1. Attacked an instance that has already been found before → a suitable message is displayed.

2. Attacked an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form, that there is a memory trail of a previously lost instance of it → that previously generated lost instance is re-created, instead of a new incremental one + a suitable message is displayed + know_of and instance_of for that particular instance are asserted.

3. Attacked an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form, while the instance list of that object is empty, i.e. that object is definitely the first

to be hit (to be found) → a new unique instance is generated + a suitable message is displayed + know_of and instance_of for the new unique instance are asserted

4. Attacked an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form for the second time (two attackeds in a single reactive feedback list) → the first hit refers to a previously found instance + the second attacked generates a new unique instance + a suitable message is displayed + know_of and instance_of for the new unique instance are asserted

5. Attacked an object (either known such as sphere or unknown such as object) in its general form, while it can refer to a previously found instance, rather than generating a new unique instance (rather than extending the instance list) → attacked refers to that previously hit (found) instance + a suitable message is displayed

6. Attacked an illegal instance (an instance that cannot possibly be recognized as that instance) → a suitable message is displayed

A succession of experiments were carried out to test CernoCAMAL's probabilistic reasoner. A sample run of the CPR is presented below.

[found(pred), found(pre), found(sphere)].

found(pred) --> pred1
found(pre) --> prey1
found(sphere) --> sphere1

==> [pred1, prey1, sphere1]

belief(apriori_prob(object, 0.0), deduction, 1, 0.75).
belief(apriori_prob(sphere, 0.3), deduction, 1, 0.75).
belief(apriori_prob(pred, 0.3), deduction, 1, 0.75).
belief(apriori_prob(pre, 0.3), deduction, 1, 0.75).

[found(sphere), hit(pre), found(sphere)].

found(sphere) --> refers to sphere1
hit(pre) --> refers to prey1
found(sphere) --> sphere2

==> [pred1, prey1, sphere1, sphere2]

belief(apriori_prob(object, 0.0), deduction, 2, 0.75).
belief(apriori_prob(sphere, 0.5), deduction, 2, 0.75).
belief(apriori_prob(pred, 0.25), deduction, 2, 0.75).
belief(apriori_prob(pre, 0.25), deduction, 2, 0.75).

[found(sphere), found(pre), attacked(pred)].

found(sphere) --> refers to either sphere1 or sphere2
found(pre) --> refers to prey1
attacked(pred) --> refers to pred1

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==> [ pred1, prey1, sphere1, sphere2 ]
belief( apriori_prob(object, 0.0),    deduction, 3, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(sphere, 0.5),    deduction, 3, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(pred, 0.25),     deduction, 3, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(pre, 0.25),      deduction, 3, 0.75 ).
-----
[ found(pred), found(sphere), near(pred) ].
found(pred)    -->    refers to prey1
found(sphere)  -->    refers to either sphere1 or sphere2
near(pred)     -->    refers to pred1
==> [ pred1, prey1, sphere1, sphere2 ]
belief( apriori_prob(object, 0.0),    deduction, 4, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(sphere, 0.5),    deduction, 4, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(pred, 0.25),     deduction, 4, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(pre, 0.25),      deduction, 4, 0.75 ).
-----
[ found(pred), lost(pred1), attacked(pred) ].
found(pred)    -->    refers to prey1
lost(pred1)    -->    refers to pred1
attacked (pred) -->    refers to previously-lost pred1
==> [ pred1, prey1, sphere1, sphere2 ]
belief( apriori_prob(object, 0.0),    deduction, 5, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(sphere, 0.5),    deduction, 5, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(pred, 0.25),     deduction, 5, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(pre, 0.25),      deduction, 5, 0.75 ).
-----
[ ate(pre), found(pred), found(pre), near(sphere) ].
ate(pre)       -->    prey1 is destroyed
found(pred)    -->    refers to pred1
found(pre)     -->    prey2 (prey1 cannot come back to
life)
near(sphere)   -->    refers to either sphere1 or sphere2
==> [ pred1, prey2, sphere1, sphere2 ]
belief( apriori_prob(object, 0.0),    deduction, 6, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(sphere, 0.5),    deduction, 6, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(pred, 0.25),     deduction, 6, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(pre, 0.25),      deduction, 6, 0.75 ).
-----
[ ate(sphere), found(pred), hit(pre), found(sphere) ].

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ate(sphere)    -->    sphere2 is destroyed (recency rule)
found(pred)    -->    refers to pred1
hit(pre)       -->    refers to prey2
found(sphere)  -->    refers to sphere1
==> [ pred1, prey2, sphere1 ]
belief( apriori_prob(object, 0.0),    deduction, 7, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(sphere, 0.3),    deduction, 7, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(pred, 0.3),     deduction, 7, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(pre, 0.3),      deduction, 7, 0.75 ).
-----
[ attacked(pred), found(pred), found(pre), found(sphere) ].
attacked(pred) -->    refers to pred1
found(pred)    -->    pred2
found(pre)     -->    refers to prey2
found(sphere)  -->    refers to sphere1
==> [ pred1, pred2, prey2, sphere1 ]
belief( apriori_prob(object, 0.0),    deduction, 8, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(sphere, 0.25),   deduction, 8, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(pred, 0.5),     deduction, 8, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(pre, 0.25),     deduction, 8, 0.75 ).
-----
[ lost(pred), found(pre), near(sphere), attacked(pred) ].
lost(pred)     -->    refers to both pred1 and pred2
found(pre)     -->    refers to prey2
near(sphere)   -->    refers to sphere1
attacked (pred) -->    refers to previously-lost pred1
==> [ pred1, prey2, sphere1 ]
belief( apriori_prob(object, 0.0),    deduction, 9, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(sphere, 0.3),    deduction, 9, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(pred, 0.3),     deduction, 9, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(pre, 0.3),      deduction, 9, 0.75 ).
-----
[ found(pred), found(pre), hit(sphere), near(sphere) ].
found(pred)    -->    refers to previously-lost pred2
found(pre)     -->    refers to prey2
hit(sphere)    -->    refers to sphere1
near(sphere)   -->    sphere3 (sphere2 cannot come back
to life)
==> [ pred1, pred2, prey2, sphere1, sphere3 ]
belief( apriori_prob(object, 0.0),    deduction, 10, 0.75 ).
belief( apriori_prob(sphere, 0.4),    deduction, 10, 0.75 ).

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belief(apriori_prob(pred, 0.4), deduction, 10, 0.75).

belief(apriori_prob(pre, 0.2), deduction, 10, 0.75).

As stated before, the frame problem describes the problem of how to keep an agent's model of its environment consistent and up to date. To most AI researchers, the frame problem is, basically, the challenge of representing the effects of actions in logic without having to represent explicitly a huge number of intuitively obvious non-effects. The CPR addresses the frame problem by limiting the scope of the propositions its deliberative component must re-consider and re-evaluate in the light of its actions by using the memory trail explained in the comprehensive set of possible elements constituting the reactive feedback list.

V. DISCUSSION

CernoCAMAL's CPR memory facility is best understood by considering Cerno in its dynamic and uncertain simulation environment. Now, suppose that Cerno starts moving around and stumbling across various objects in the testbed. Cerno's findings are represented as reactive feedback lists that are passed to the deliberative component for reasoning and deliberation. Having found a domain object or perhaps an unidentified one, Cerno reasons about the probabilities of various objects and their instances being present in the environment. Now, suppose that Cerno loses or eats (destroys) an item, e.g. a sphere or prey. That lost or eaten (destroyed) object or instance is withdrawn from the simulation world. The way Cerno limits the scope of the propositions it must re-consider and re-evaluate in the light of its actions is by the loss' or destruction's memory trail that is formed by the CernoCAMAL's CPR. The object and instance reasoning of CernoCAMAL's CPR using memory trails is perhaps the most significant part of the probabilistic reasoning carried out in the deliberative layer of the architecture, as well as the most significant contribution of this work. It is for this reason that the greatest emphasis is placed on the tests and experiments that validate the correct functionality of the CPR. In a nutshell, when an instance is found :

- If the instance list of that object is empty (i.e. if that object is definitely the first to be found), then a new unique instance is generated.
- If there is a memory trail of a previously lost instance, then that previously generated lost instance is re-created, instead of re-generating a new incremental one.
- If the found instance can refer to a previously found instance, rather than generating a new unique instance (rather than extending the instance list), then it refers to that previously found instance.
- If the found instance has been found for a second time, then the first one refers to a previously found instance and the second one generates a new unique instance.
- If an instance was eaten, then the trail for that instance will be marked as 'destroyed' so that upon finding an instance, the identification is made based on the fact that it cannot possibly be that destroyed instance. Put crudely, an eaten object or instance cannot come back to life.

CernoCAMAL as a Probabilistic-BDI cognitive architecture has pursued a perspective informed by affective and motivational control states, rationalized by cognitive models of probabilistic reasoning. It presents a vigorous affect-

and affordance-based core for mind, as the Probabilistic-BDI model is now valenced via affective values and affordances, allowing the entire BDI model to run using numeric affective values to prioritize choices over the current belief set. The current CAMAL research has now taken a number of new directions, as researchers pursue their own agenda. These new directions take the original design associated with the overarching CAMAL architecture, together with the concept of an underlying affect and affordance mechanism that can be used to compare process priority or rank goals and intentions but reframe the research according to specific interests or needs [11]. Using a real mobile robot, along with a new vision system will be the next step, resulting in a deeper perceptual anchoring model. This new perceptual anchoring model could combine the improved sensors of the new robot with neural learning mechanisms and may, therefore, address some of the issues raised by Barsalou [32].

There clearly existed a need to address and incorporate probabilistic reasoning and inference in CAMAL. The primary aim of the CernoCAMAL research project was to tackle this need with the formal probability and Bayesian theories. This research, therefore, attempted to address the following specific research questions in the current cognitive architecture under investigation:

- Can CernoCAMAL reason probabilistically by exploiting the proposed EBS? Can the integration of the proposed EBS facilitate probabilistic reasoning and inference in CernoCAMAL?

Yes. In light of the overall collection of experimental results, CernoCAMAL can reason probabilistically by exploiting the proposed EBS. In other words, the integration of the proposed EBS facilitated probabilistic reasoning and inference in CernoCAMAL. This was specifically validated and confirmed, as correct operation of the CernoCAMAL's CPR in terms of probabilistic object / instance reasoning was tested comprehensively.

- Can the Bayesian-BDI model run compatibly with the affect and motivational models, and affective and motivational valences used throughout the whole architecture? Can this ensure a consistent metric across all aspects of affect, reasoning, and domain model management?

The correct results and expected operations of the processes indicated the compatibility of the Bayesian BDI model with the affect and motivational valences used throughout the architecture. This provides a consistent control language for ordering propositions, selecting goals, constructing a plan of action, forming a focused belief with an updated degree of belief, and prioritising processes. It ensures a consistent metric across all aspects of affect, reasoning, and domain model management.

- Can the probabilistic deliberation results of the CPR be used for computing changing degrees of belief given apriori, and subsequently using the Bayesian-BDI, affect, and motivational models to determine the agent's intentions, actions, or behaviours?

The performed CPR tests confirmed and validated that the CernoCAMAL's probabilistic reasoner can deliberate using the EBS and assumed degrees of belief, infer posterior probabilities correctly, assign them to the appropriate belief descriptors, and reason probabilistically about the number of

objects and their instances that may be present in the environment.

- Can the CernoCAMAL cognitive architecture be applied to virtual and physical cognitive agents using synthetic testbeds and mobile robots?

The succession of experiments in simulation and robotic testbeds, by successfully applying the CernoCAMAL cognitive architecture to virtual and physical cognitive agents, showed improvements and increased efficacy in CernoCAMAL's overall cognitive performance, as well as specific achievements in light of the overall collection of experiments.

The current CAMAL research has now taken a number of new directions, as researchers pursue their own agenda. These new directions take the original design associated with the overarching CAMAL architecture, together with the concept of an underlying affect and affordance mechanism that can be used to compare process priority and rank goals and intentions but re-frame the research according to specific interests or needs [11].

Using a more sophisticated mobile robot such as a P3DX [31] along with a new vision system and camera could be the next step, resulting in a more accurate object identification and consequently a deeper perceptual anchoring model. This new perceptual model could combine the input from the improved sensors of the new robot with apriori information included in the domain model. The new robot would be more adaptable and capable of working in unknown and uncertain environments. This is loosely related to the UK Computing Research Committee's Grand Challenge Number Five: Architecture of Brain and Mind [33]. GC5 is a multidisciplinary attempt to understand and integrate natural intelligence and high-level cognitive processes at various levels of abstraction. The aim is to demonstrate the results of our improved understanding in a succession of increasingly sophisticated working robots.

Another next step could be regarding the manual incorporation of shallow Bayesian metacognitive norms. Currently, CernoCAMAL does not deliberate to determine which norm should be used in the motivational blackboard. This means that the Bayesian norms have to be pre-programmed prior to start-up (hand-coded and defined in the domain model). This manual incorporation could be improved upon by constructing more norms and deliberating to choose one that has already yielded greater task effectiveness in the past.

In addition to the above two specific ways of improving the CernoCAMAL architecture, there are still plenty of open issues in cognitive architectures research that deserve attention and effort from researchers in the area, despite the many advances that have occurred during almost four decades of research and work. An outstanding issue is that each existing cognitive architecture exhibits many of the capacities described in this thesis and elsewhere, but few support all of them. However, a cognitive architecture as a UTC was defined as: a single set of mechanisms and processes for all cognitive behaviour. The research community should perhaps devote more resources to trying to unify the existing capacities and capabilities into one universal and comprehensive framework of cognition.

Moreover, methods for the evaluation and assessment of cognitive architectures and their cognitive abilities could be broadened to include more realistic terrains. Metrics like those

used in this thesis for experimentation purposes are necessary, but not sufficient to provide an accurate way of comparing and contrasting competing architectures and cognitive systems. Despite evaluating various cognitive performances in different testbeds, more complex environments must be created, both physical and simulated, that exercise these cognitive capabilities and provide realistic opportunities for measurement [34]. Experimental comparisons among competing architectures can play an important role in measuring key variables in unbiased and informative ways. On the positive side, we now have over four decades worth of experience and development with constructing and using a variety of cognitive architectures for a wide range of problems and terrains

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Cognition is better viewed as solving probabilistic, rather than logical, inference problems; meaning cognition is better understood in terms of probability theory, rather than in terms of logic [35, 36]. The probabilistic approach to cognition has, therefore, become an established approach in recent decades – something that this body of work took advantage of.

This paper presents a Probabilistic-BDI affective-motivational cognitive architecture. There are many views on what constitutes a cognitive architecture or the place of affect and motivation in a cognitive architecture though. CernoCAMAL pursued a perspective informed by affective and motivational control states, rationalized by a cognitive model of probabilistic reasoning using degrees of belief. Any thesis that deals with cognition and cognitive architectures needs some explanation as to its scope and focus. The scope and focus of the current cognitive architecture under investigation was to extend the original overarching cognitive architecture of CAMAL to enable it to reason probabilistically about domain model objects through perception, and also integrate Bayesian formalism into its BDI model to coalesce a number of mechanisms, in line with the Gibsonian affect and affordance theory, as well as Davis's theory of affect [10, 11, 37].

The succession of experiments in simulation and robotic testbeds established improvements in CernoCAMAL's cognitive performance and probabilistic inference over the original CAMAL. In applying the CernoCAMAL cognitive architecture to RoboCAMAL platform, the minuscule number of wrong associations showed that the percentage of failures was negligible, thus RoboCAMAL performance improved by the application of CernoCAMAL architecture. CernoCAMAL effectively presents a vigorous affect- and affordance-based core for mind, as the Bayesian-BDI model is now valenced via affective values and affordances, allowing the entire BDI schema to run using numeric affective values to prioritize choices over the current belief set. Since affect is used across the cognitive architecture as a decision metric, affective values can be thought of as a currency. The BDI model that lacked an affective decision metric consistent with the affordances used in the affect and motivational models, is now grounded consistently in the use of affect.

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